

Conductance measurements of narcotic-analgesic drugs in ethanol + water mixtures at 25°C

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The conductance data of drugs namely Parvon Spas (PS), Parvodex (PD) and Tramacip (TM) in ethanol (EtOH)-water (H₂O) mixtures at 298 K have been analysed in absence as well as presence of additives viz. electrolyte – sodium chloride (NaCl), surfactant sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS), non-electrolytes – fructose and sucrose (C₆H₁₂O₆ and C₁₂H₂₂O₁₁) by least square fitting method. Increase in specific conductance, equivalent conductance and limiting molar conductance is observed as the content of EtOH decreases in EtOH-H₂O mixtures. However, with the addition of above-mentioned additives, the magnitude of Λ_0 values increase to different extent for different additives. In general, the present drugs in EtOH-H₂O solvent system behave as weak electrolytes. The results obtained from these studies can be of immense use for pharmacological application of drugs.

Most drugs are organic molecules with both hydrophilic and hydrophobic groups. These molecules often contain certain groups, which are responsible for their acidic, basic or amphoteric properties. Pharmacological¹⁻⁴ properties of drug are highly dependent on the solution behaviour. These drug molecules show specific interactions with lipid molecules due to hydrophobic groups, and due to hydrophilic groups, they show electrostatic interactions as well. Thus the knowledge of physico-chemical properties of drug plays an important role to understand its physiological action. In continuation to our work on conductance measurements^{5,6} of electrolytes and non-electrolytes in binary solvent systems, in the present paper, conductance study has been carried out for the drugs Parvon Spas, Parvodex and Tramacip in EtOH-H₂O mixtures at 25°C.

Results and discussion

The drug PS consists of three components i.e. dextropropoxyphene hydrochloride (65 mg), dicyclomine hydrochloride (10 mg) and paracetamol (400 mg). Drug PD contains only one component i.e. dextropropoxyphene hydrochloride while TM contains tramadol hydrochloride. The different components of studied drugs have following structures⁷.

(1) Dextropropoxyphene hydrochloride [C₂₂H₂₉NO₂HCl], mol. wt. 375

[(1*S*,2*R*)-1-Benzyl-3-dimethylamino-2-methyl-1-phenylpropylpropionate hydrochloride]

(2) Dicyclomine hydrochloride [C₁₉H₃₅NO₂HCl], mol. wt. 345.5

2-(Diethylamino)ethyl[bicyclohexyl]-1-carboxylate hydrochloride

(3) Paracetamol [C₈H₉NO₂], mol. wt. 151

N-(4-Hydroxyphenyl)acetamide

(4) Tramadol hydrochloride [$C_{16}H_{25}NO_2 \cdot HCl$],
mol. wt. 299.84

cis-2-(Dimethylamino)-1-(3-methoxyphenyl)-cyclohexanol
hydrochloride

The molar concentrations and the corresponding molar conductances ($\Lambda/\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) of the drugs PS, PD and TM in EtOH-H₂O mixtures in absence of additives have been presented in Table 1.

Equivalent conductance values for these drugs have also been measured in the presence of additives e.g. sodium chloride (NaCl), sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS), fructose (C₆H₁₂O₆) and sucrose (C₁₂H₂₂O₁₁). The Λ and κ values, and the corresponding concentration (C) values for these systems have been summarized in Table 2.

The limiting molar conductances Λ_0 ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) for these drugs have been obtained under different set of concentration range from the linear plots of Λ vs $C^{1/2}$ in the absence and presence of additives by least squares fitting method and are reported in Table 3.

It is evident from Table 1 that equivalent conductance values decrease with the addition of drug in each studied solvent system. The specific conductance values at one specific concentration decrease with the decrease of water content in the EtOH-H₂O solvent mixtures as shown in Fig. 1. This is in accordance with the nature of solvent system as with the decrease of ethanol component to EtOH-H₂O mixtures, dielectric constant of the system increases thereby decreasing intermolecular attraction between solvent molecules, and hence increasing conductance values.

Equivalent conductance decreases with the increase of concentration of NaCl for a (Table 2) particular solvent system. However, equivalent conductance increase with increase of water content (due to increase of dielectric constant) to EtOH-H₂O solvent system. Same is true for all the studied drugs in presence of other additives, namely, SDS, sucrose and fructose. At around one fixed concentration of drugs ($\approx 5.4 \times 10^{-4}$) the Λ values for studied drugs in the presence of additives change as follows :

NaCl > SDS > sucrose > fructose > without additives.

The equivalent conductance data for tramadol hydro-

Table1. Equivalent conductance data for Parvon Spas, Parvodex and Tramacip in various aqueous solvent mixtures of EtOH

Mol% EtOH →	90	70	50	30
$C \times 10^4$	Λ	Λ	Λ	Λ
Parvon Spas :				
5.4	4.07	4.30	5.84	6.68
10.8	3.15	3.18	4.26	4.99
16.2	2.81	2.81	3.76	4.45
21.5	2.60	2.64	3.51	4.22
26.8	2.49	2.53	3.37	4.08
32.0	2.41	2.47	3.25	3.95
37.1	2.37	2.42	3.17	3.88
42.3	2.32	2.39	3.10	3.79
47.3	2.30	2.35	3.06	3.74
52.3	2.30	2.34	3.03	3.66
Parvodex :				
2.64	23.57	29.86	33.01	42.44
5.27	18.89	21.26	24.41	30.71
7.87	17.40	18.98	22.14	26.89
10.4	16.75	18.35	19.95	25.93
12.9	16.40	17.69	19.62	24.77
15.5	16.06	17.40	19.00	24.09
18.0	15.90	16.83	18.80	23.51
20.4	15.86	16.68	18.50	23.19
22.9	15.76	16.49	18.30	22.83
25.3	15.74	16.40	18.04	22.80
Tramacip :				
2.9	11.3	12.1	15.74	21.4
5.9	8.5	9.5	10.5	16.3
8.8	7.8	8.6	8.9	13.8
11.7	7.4	8.1	8.5	12.7
14.6	7.1	7.8	7.9	12.4
17.4	6.9	7.7	7.6	11.9
20.2	6.8	7.5	7.4	11.8
23.0	6.7	7.4	7.3	11.3
25.8	6.7	7.3	7.2	11.2
28.5	6.6	7.2	7.1	11.0

chloride in the presence of SDS additive have also been presented in Fig. 2.

Studies⁸ involving organic additives that are solubilized by the micelle formation have primarily dealt with their effect on the CMC, aggregation number and their location in the micelle interior. In the present work, however, the effect of surfactant, SDS is viewed in terms of its effect on solution behaviour of drugs mentioned above.

Table 2. Equivalent conductance data for Parvon Spas, Parvodex and Tramacip in presence of additives in various aqueous solvent mixtures of EtOH

Mole% EtOH	Parvon Spas			Parvodex			Tramacip		
	70	50	30	70	50	30	70	50	30
$C \times 10^4$	Λ	Λ	Λ	Λ	Λ	Λ	Λ	Λ	Λ
NaCl additive :									
8.4	109.1	126.9	191.1	380.1	594.2	735.6	149.2	174.3	222.8
16.8	70.8	82.7	119.5	277.9	348.7	408.4	90.4	105.7	136.1
25.1	58.3	67.2	95.8	214.9	267.0	303.2	71.0	83.3	103.0
33.3	51.5	59.8	85.3	184.1	226.8	251.3	61.4	72.2	92.5
41.4	47.6	55.5	79.1	166.0	202.5	220.5	55.6	65.1	83.7
49.5	44.6	52.3	74.7	153.4	184.0	199.4	51.3	60.3	77.7
57.4	42.7	50.3	71.8	144.9	171.4	184.8	48.5	57.1	73.3
65.3	41.1	48.6	71.0	138.5	162.1	173.9	46.2	54.7	70.0
73.2	39.9	47.3	69.3	133.8	155.1	165.3	44.4	52.7	67.4
80.9	38.9	46.4	67.4	130.3	149.8	158.8	43.3	51.2	65.4
SDS additive :									
24.6	47.0	49.2	58.8	106.6	128.0	166.1	57.1	69.8	84.1
48.7	34.2	35.4	42.9	72.8	84.2	106.1	38.1	44.8	56.0
72.2	28.8	31.0	37.1	59.4	70.4	84.0	31.8	36.7	46.1
95.2	26.2	28.5	34.4	52.7	63.2	72.4	28.5	32.8	41.3
117.6	24.5	27.2	32.6	48.3	59.2	64.8	26.6	30.2	38.4
139.5	23.4	26.0	31.4	44.7	57.5	59.0	25.4	28.6	36.1
160.9	22.5	25.2	30.4	42.2	55.7	54.4	24.5	27.3	34.5
181.8	21.8	24.6	29.7	40.5	53.9	50.7	23.6	26.3	33.4
202.2	21.3	24.2	29.1	38.9	53.6	47.6	23.1	25.6	32.3
222.2	20.8	23.9	28.6	37.7	53.2	45.0	22.6	25.0	31.5
241.7	20.4	23.6	28.1	36.6	52.7	42.8	22.2	24.5	30.8
260.8	20.1	23.2	21.8	35.8	52.5	40.9	21.8	24.1	30.4
Sucrose additive :									
2.4	217.8	249.0	325.0	688.2	899.1	1186.2	371.7	449.5	567.1
4.9	105.0	118.5	157.5	335.3	437.8	579.3	177.8	210.0	270.1
7.3	69.9	77.8	104.6	223.9	292.7	387.7	118.2	138.7	177.9
9.8	51.6	57.5	70.0	166.0	217.2	287.9	87.2	102.4	130.8
12.1	41.5	46.3	62.0	133.7	175.2	232.9	69.9	82.3	104.9
14.5	34.3	38.3	51.5	111.3	145.9	194.0	58.1	68.1	87.2
16.9	29.2	32.6	43.9	95.2	124.9	166.2	49.6	58.1	74.4
19.2	25.5	28.5	38.4	83.6	109.8	146.1	43.4	51.0	65.2
21.5	22.7	25.4	34.1	74.5	97.8	130.2	38.6	45.3	57.9
23.8	20.5	23.0	30.8	67.3	88.2	117.5	34.8	40.8	51.9
Fructose additive :									
13.4	37.4	45.8	60.7	121.7	159.4	210.5	64.4	73.3	94.4
26.7	18.4	22.0	29.9	60.3	79.2	104.9	31.5	36.0	46.3
39.9	12.1	14.5	19.6	40.0	52.7	69.7	20.8	23.7	30.2
52.9	9.1	10.8	14.7	29.9	39.5	52.3	15.4	17.6	22.9
65.8	7.2	8.6	11.7	23.9	31.6	41.8	12.2	14.0	18.2

Table-2 (contd.)

78.6	6.0	7.1	9.7	26.3	26.3	34.9	10.1	11.6	15.2
91.3	5.1	6.1	22.6	17.0	22.6	30.0	8.7	9.9	13.0
103.8	4.4	5.3	19.8	14.9	19.8	26.3	7.6	8.6	11.3
116.2	3.9	4.7	17.6	13.3	17.6	23.4	6.7	7.7	10.0
128.5	3.5	4.2	5.8	12.0	15.9	21.1	6.1	6.9	9.0

Table 3. Limiting molar conductance data for drugs in absence as well as in presence of additives in various aqueous solvent mixtures of EtOH

Mole % EtOH→	90	70	50	30
Parvon Spas (PS) :				
In the absence of additives	2.76	2.88	3.92	5.29
NaCl	-	76.72	83.15	113.0
SDS	-	30.80	32.91	38.46
Sucrose	-	84.30	93.50	109.02
Fructose	-	15.63	18.16	24.41
Parvodex (PD) :				
In the absence of additives	23.99	30.22	34.21	43.60
NaCl	-	432.73	638.92	784.571
SDS	-	119.02	134.52	187.80
Sucrose	-	740.341	966.88	1276.39
Fructose	-	131.485	172.34	227.70
Tramacip (TM) :				
In the absence of additives	11.01	11.37	11.53	16.84
NaCl	-	92.20	107.87	139.69
SDS	-	33.69	38.43	48.10
Sucrose	-	187.50	221.66	275.74
Fructose	-	29.53	33.77	38.62

Table 3 summarize Λ_0 values of PS, PD and TM in aqueous mixtures of EtOH in absence and presence of various additives. It is clear that in the absence of additives, the Λ_0 values in general increase with decrease of EtOH content i.e. with the increase of dielectric constant for all studied drugs. For a particular solvent system, the Λ_0 values change as

$$PS < TM < PD$$

This can be explained on the basis of the structures of these drugs. TM and PD are single component system, where as PS has three components having small amount of PD. PD has simple hydrochloride group and hence, contributes maximum to conductance values. However, such small

Fig. 1. Plot of specific conductance vs composition of EtOH for PS, TM and PD at concentration $5.4 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

Fig. 2. Plot of equivalent conductance vs $C^{1/2} \times 10^{-2}$ for TM in presence of SDS additive in various compositions of EtOH.

magnitudes of these values in aqueous alcoholic systems indicate that these drugs behave as weak electrolytes. This is probably due to the incomplete dissociation and bulky size of drug in a particular solvent system.

Further, it is observed that an increase in Λ_0 values for PS, PD and TM in the presence of NaCl as additive has been observed in comparison to Λ_0 values in absence of additive, which may be due to strong electrolytic nature and conductance nature of NaCl. However, the magnitude of these conductance values is less than the Λ_0 values for NaCl in water ($\Lambda_0_{\text{NaCl}}=140$). This may be due to the partial dissociation of NaCl in the studied solvent system.

The apparent difference in the behaviour of drugs in the presence of NaCl and SDS can be viewed by the difference in magnitude of Λ_0 values (Table 3) which can be accounted for hydrophobic and electrostatic interactions. Though NaCl and SDS both have the same cation (Na^+) but due to difference in their nature, there is significant difference in conductance values. Difference in the behaviour of drugs in the presence of NaCl and SDS may be regarded as being a combination of hydrophobic and electrostatic effects in case of SDS and only electrostatic in case of NaCl. The manner in which the electrolyte ions modify the environment of drug is markedly dependent upon the nature of the constituent ions, for example, salts such as alkali metal halides modify the environment mainly by polar forces. Surfactant on the other hand, do so by polar forces as well as hydrophobic interaction⁸.

From Table 3, it is evident that magnitude of Λ_0 in the presence of sucrose and fructose increases in both cases because of their structure breaker behaviour⁹. However, the increase observed is more in case of sucrose as compared to fructose. This may be due to much larger size and breaking of sucrose to fructose and glucose which in turn gives more number of hydroxy groups to interact and hence causes more structural rearrangement in EtOH-H₂O solvent system.

The limiting molar conductance for studied additives changes as follows :

From the above studies, it can be concluded that, in general the present drugs in EtOH-H₂O solvent system behave as weak electrolytes. The conductance values, however, show changes with the nature of drug/drug combination and

nature of additives namely, electrolyte NaCl, surfactant SDS and non-electrolyte sucrose and fructose. The results obtained from these studies can be used for pharmacological application of drugs.

Experimental

The drugs Parvon Spas, Parvodex, Tramacip and additives NaCl, SDS, fructose and sucrose were used as such after drying in vacuum oven. Ethanol was kept overnight in the 4 Å molecular sieves. After decantation, it was refluxed for 2–3 h and then distilled slowly through a long fractionating column. Doubly distilled water was used for conductivity measurements.

EtOH-H₂O mixtures containing 90, 70, 50, 30, mole % of EtOH were prepared by volume. In addition, stock solution of drug was prepared with the addition of fixed amount (0.2 g) of drug in 10 ml of above solvent compositions for conductance measurements in absence of additives.

For measurement of conductance in presence of additives, a fixed weighed amount of each drug (0.2 g) was added to 40 ml of 70, 50, 30 mole % of EtOH solutions. Stock solutions of weighed amount of SDS (0.6 g), NaCl (0.1 g), sucrose (0.2 g), fructose (0.5 g) with various solvent compositions of EtOH-H₂O were also prepared. Then conductance of these solutions was measured by adding different volumes of stock solutions of different concentrations of various additives.

Conductance measurements were carried out at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$ in a water thermostat by using Shedlovsky¹⁰ conductivity cell. For each composition, the additive concentration for stock solution and drug concentration was kept constant. The conductance measurements for added drug and additive were repeated at least four times. The reproducibility of present conductance measurement is found to be $\pm 0.2\%$.

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